

COGNITIVE PROBLEMS OF UZBEK-ENGLISH TRANSLATION

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Abstract. This article deals with the cognitive-semantic analysis of the meanings of words in English and Uzbek and their translation problems, one of the most pressing problems of modern linguistics and the study of typology of languages in English and Uzbek languages.

Key word: translation problem. Cultural concepts, cognitive and communicative activity.

Translation has been formed in the culture and history of the peoples of the world for many years and is one of the types of creative activities that has been developing over the years. By translating a concept or phrase from one language into another, people exchange ideas and learn about other people's cultures, customs, and traditions.

Through translation, economic, political and cultural cooperation has been established amongst the countries of the world. This, in turn, paved the way for the comprehensive development of states. That is why translation and interpretation are so important in the language industry today.

The cognitive activity of the individual is the mental processes that provide the processing of information and as a result of which special structures of consciousness. In this regard, language as a type of cognitive and communicative activity is considered by cognitologists as a system of signs that take part in encoding and transmitting information about the environment, that is, language is a means of representing the structure of knowledge that is formed in the human mind.

In other words, information about the world is first constructed (or conceptualized) and only then verbalized. This interpretation of the language predetermines the need to take into account the interaction of language structures with other cognitive components of informing, in particular, with conceptual structures.

The cognitive activity of the individual as an integral part of his consciousness occurs in a certain cultural context. In particular, ethical norms, political and religious orientations, different components of culture largely influence the process of cognitive activity[2;45].

According to R. Jackendoff, the main constituents of the conceptual structures are basic concepts - ideas about an object, its parts, movement, action, place (space) time, signs. Basic concepts are inherent all languages, since they correlate with grammatical categories and mark distribution of words into parts of speech¹.

However, in the process (and as a result) of fragmentation, modification and unification of concepts (which is again due to a peculiar vision and perception of the surrounding world), each language acquires its own, inherent only to it conceptual characteristics that are reflected in the features of its grammar and vocabulary.

Modern translation studies considers translation as a form of intercultural communication and, focusing on the cultural context, defines culture as complex «system of systems» consisting of various subsystems such as literature, science and technology.

National-cultural marking predetermines the fact that there can be no ideally symmetrical cultural concepts. The structure of the concept, and in particular the

¹ Jackendoff R. Sense and reference in a psychologically based semantics // Talking minds. Cambridge: Cambridge University, 1984. P. 49-72.

cultural one, consists of the core (the most relevant denotations and connotations for native speakers) and the periphery (less significant connotations and individual associations) between which there are no clear boundaries[4;56].

And even when the outer shell concept (its conceptual side) and the core of the concept in the source and recipient cultures coincide, the less persistent and meaningful connotations that evoke the concept in the reader of the original will never completely coincide with the “periphery” of the corresponding concept in the reader of the translation.

Cultural concepts can be either partially equivalent in different cultures or purely specific to a particular culture, that is, non-equivalent.

In this regard, some researchers propose a relatively new concept - conceptual translation.

Translation is considered as a continuous process of interpreting the concepts of one culture through the concepts of another, providing the formation of equivalent relations between objects (cultures), while the equivalence can only be relative, interpretation, and the task of the translator is to contribute to a more complete disclosure of the original cultural object.

Regardless of the manner, the purpose of translation, what and in which branch we are translating, there are two elements in the basics of translation – the meaning and content. Translators and translatoologists differ in which of those two elements they prioritize – meaning or content.

However, prioritizing one of them does not always give the expected results. For example, in the cases when coming across with the units that are impossible to translate – realia, idiomatic constructions, it is required to prioritize the content, the artistry and expressiveness are subordinated by the target language means.

For example, when rendering into another, unrelated language such Russian lexemes as *okroshka*, *bulochka*, *pechka*, Uzbek lexemes as **chuchvara**, *manti*,

sandal, suri, mahsi, to'n, and English lexemes as *dozen, mile, football, machine, meter, pound, sterling, pudding, dressing* will definitely lead to a certain degree of the content loss.

But it is such cases that require language skills and knowledge from the translator. The same thing is observed in grammatical phenomena as well. This is true because grammatical rules and meanings, peculiarities and qualities provide specificity of every single language[7;76].

For example, such Uzbek language units as *mahsi, go'ja, sumalak*, can be rendered into another language using explanation.

So, the requirements of equivalence in the translation of emotive prose differ considerably from these in other styles where form merely serves to convey the content of the utterance and do not fulfill any expressive and aesthetic function (publicist style in all its genres being to a certain extent an exception). In these styles, stylistic means and devices are merely used as their indispensable markers.

Also, translation plays a significant role not only in teaching and learning processes of language education, but also it is very important to convey the one's mentality, customs and traditions which exist in their cultures. Therefore, there is a great amount of necessity for different types of translation studies. Knowing how the translations works can help learners to compare and understand different aspects of the different nations and cultures.

Since you are required to understand and know, easily follow the meaning of the given text or contexts while you are learning a foreign language. Interestingly, when you begin to investigate a culture or deal with any foreign language learning, you will definitely have to work with the texts and literary resources.

As a result of that, most of translators and language providers need to face some challenges which can be real obstacles for readers and learners of the language which is being learned or taught. Moreover, the translated forms of materials or resources for investigation, assist to express and understand the

meaning of the texts and literary works.

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